

Potentiometric Study of the Complexes of Trivalent Yttrium, Lanthanum, Praseodymium, Neodymium, Gadolinium, Terbium, Dysprosium and Holmium with Solochrome Black 6BN

J. R. NARKHEDE*, G. S. NATRAJAN and S. P. SANGAL
Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur University,
Nagpur-440 010

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SPPECTROPHOTOMETRIC and potentiometric studies on the complexes of yttrium, lanthanum, cerium and neodymium with SB 6B have been reported¹. The potentiometric study involving the complexation and stepwise formation of the complexes of yttrium(III), lanthanum(III), praseodymium(III), neodymium(III), gadolinium(III), terbium(III), dysprosium(III) and holmium(III) with SB 6B in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan have been reported in the present communication. The 'practical' proton-ligand stability constants of the ligand and the metal-ligand stability constant (stepwise) have been obtained by Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique², as used by Irving and Rossotti³. The overall free energy changes (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) associated with the equilibrium shown in equation (1) are also reported,

where R^{3+} represents the metal ions and A^{m-} the SB 6B anion.

Experimental

Stock solutions ($1.65 \times 10^{-3} M$) of rare earth chlorides were prepared in perchloric acid to prevent hydrolysis and standardised⁴. Sodium salt of SB 6B (BDH) was converted to the corresponding acid⁵ and its stock solution ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) was prepared in 50% dioxan-water media; dioxan was purified by reported method⁶. The solution of the ligand and solutions of CO_2 -free sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) and 0.1 M perchloric acid (Riedel) were standardised potentiometrically by usual procedures. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) solution was prepared in double-distilled water.

A Systronics 322-1 pH-meter with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used to determine the changes in hydrogen ion concentrations. A thermostatically controlled water-bath (accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$) was used.

Three different mixtures were prepared containing (acid), (acid+ligand) and (acid+ligand+metal ion), such that the concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in all the cases. Neutral sodium perchlorate solution was added to maintain the ionic strength ($\mu=0.1 M$). The metal-ligand ratio was kept at 1 : 3. The difference in amount

of sodium hydroxide utilised for the last two titrations is a measure of the extent of complexation.

To calculate the formation constants of ligand proton system, the values of $\bar{n}_A$ at different pH were calculated using the acid and ligand titration curves. The formation curves at different temperatures were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}_A$ vs pH. The metal-ligand stability constants were obtained from the analysis of metal-ligand formation curves drawn between $\bar{n}$ and pL. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been calculated as reported⁷.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves it is observed that the metal-ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curve, which proves that the liberation of proton could be due to chelation. Various computational methods⁸, viz. interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values and graphical method were applied to obtain the stepwise proton-ligand stability constants and metal-ligand stability constants. The mean of proton-ligand formation constants, metal-ligand stability constants at an ionic strength of 0.1 M (NaClO₄) and at different temperatures have been summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—AVERAGE VALUES OF PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SB 6B ($\mu=0.1$ M)

Constants	30°	40°	50°
$\log K_1^H$	12.19	11.44	10.68
$\log K_2^H$	7.54	7.41	7.27
$\log \beta_3^H$	19.73	18.85	17.95

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES ($\mu=0.1$ M)

Metal(III)	log K_1 values		
	30°	40°	50°
Y	13.55	12.98	12.40
La	11.25	10.68	10.13
Pr	12.43	11.86	11.28
Nd	12.47	11.88	11.31
Gd	13.37	12.77	12.17
Tb	13.80	13.14	12.46
Dy	13.82	13.20	12.58
Ho	13.96	13.28	12.62

Comparing the stability constants of the rare earths with SB 6B, we observe that the order of stability of rare earth complexes is La < Pr < Nd < Gd < Y < Tb < Dy < Ho; and also with change in temperature the order is 30° > 40° > 50°. The values of thermodynamic parameters are summarised in Table 3.

The ligand SB 6B has three dissociable protons. The proton of SO₃H group was assumed to be completely dissociated under the experimental conditions as no detectable lowering of the pH value was observed when the ligand was added to the perchloric acid solution. The maximum value of $\bar{n}$ was 1.05 at an apparent pH 6.5 which approximately is

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Metal(III)	ΔG (kcal mol ⁻¹)			ΔH (kcal mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
	30°	40°	50°	30-50°	30-50°
Y	18.79	18.60	18.33	26.10	23.97
La	15.60	15.30	14.97	25.10	31.31
Pr	17.24	16.99	16.68	25.65	27.66
Nd	17.29	17.02	16.72	26.27	29.56
Gd	18.54	18.30	17.99	26.69	26.81
Tb	19.14	18.83	18.42	30.04	35.82
Dy	19.17	18.91	18.60	27.71	28.10
Ho	19.36	19.03	18.66	29.87	34.63

the hydrolysis region of the rare earth metal ions. Thus, the formation of only 1:1 complex is observed below the hydrolysis range of all the metals under study.

A plot of $\log K_1$ vs Z^2/r^{3+} (where Z is the charge and r^{3+} is the ionic radius of the metals) indicates the 'discontinuous' nature of gadolinium⁹.

In the complexation, lanthanum and gadolinium have low or halting values for stability constants as compared to the values of other rare earths studied, which have no observed d -electrons¹⁰. Spectroscopic evidence also indicate the unavailability of well-shielded $4f$ electrons for bond formation¹¹.

It is also seen that the $\log K_1$ values for Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Dy^{III}-Ho^{III} are very close to each other, which is in agreement with that reported by Vickery¹². The observed $\log K_1$ values for Y^{III}, Tb^{III} and Dy^{III} are close to each other. This type of trend has been reported by Latimer¹³. The values of ΔG of complexation between the rare earths studied and SB 6B show a reverse trend to those of $\log K_1$ values. The ΔG values also represent the same trend as the $\log K_1$ values, such as 'discontinuous' nature of lanthanum gadolinium⁹ and similar nature of praseodymium-neodymium and dysprosium-holmium groups¹². The values of ΔH indicate the strong complex formation in this case¹⁴. Negative values of ΔS for the complex formation are also justified¹⁵.

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